

Perception of the Family Adoption Program Among MBBS Undergraduates in a Private Medical College: A Cross-Sectional Analysis from Central India

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ABSTRACT

Background: The Family Adoption Program (FAP) is a pioneering initiative aimed at promoting community-based learning and healthcare delivery among medical undergraduates. The program involves the adoption of families by medical students trained by faculties of Community Medicine department, then only they provide comprehensive healthcare services, health education, and promote preventive measures to improve the overall well-being of their adopted families.

Objectives: To assess the perception of FAP among MBBS students in a private medical college of Central India.

Methodology: The cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Community Medicine at Sri Aurobindo Medical College and Postgraduate Institute (SAMC & PGI), Indore, Madhya Pradesh among MBBS students of 2021 and 2022 batch. A predesigned, semi-structured questionnaire was completed by all participants with the help of google form during their practical class. A total of 240 responses from the 2021 batch and 229 responses from the 2022 batch was obtained. Appropriate statistical analysis was done at the end of study.

Results: A total of 469 MBBS students (2021 and 2022 batch) participated in the study, showing positive experiences with the Family Adoption Program (FAP). The majority reported improved communication skills, sufficient faculty support, and perceived FAP as necessary for their professional development. Overall, FAP was found to be beneficial for MBBS students.

Conclusion-The study concludes that the Family Adoption Program (FAP) is a valuable learning experience for MBBS students, enhancing their communication skills, community exposure, and professional development.

Recommendations-Increase awareness and knowledge of FAP, improve community exposure, enhance faculty support, and consider making FAP a mandatory part of the medical curriculum along with regular health camps.

Key words: FAP, MBBS Students, Field experience, Communication skills, Exposure, Professional Development.

INTRODUCTION

The Family Adoption Program (FAP) by the National Medical Commission (NMC) is a strategic initiative to integrate family-centred care and longitudinal patient relationships into medical education. The program provides medical students with hands-on experience in managing long-term patient relationships, enhancing their clinical skills and understanding of family dynamics.¹ The FAP provides a chance for medical schools to innovate their curriculum and integrate new teaching methodologies that emphasize real-world experiences. The FAP strengthens ties between medical institutions

and the community by involving families in the educational process, potentially leading to better community health outcomes.²

Objectives-

To assess the perception of FAP among MBBS students in a private medical college of Central India.

METHODOLOGY

Study Setting

The study was conducted in the Department of Community Medicine at Sri Aurobindo Medical College and Postgraduate Institute (SAMC & PGI), Indore, Madhya Pradesh.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study

Study Participants

Two batches of MBBS students (2021 and 2022) were included in the study. All students who actively participated in the practical class were included. Students absent in practical that day were excluded.

Sample Size

Convenient sampling was used, as each batch of MBBS has a strength of 250 students. A total of 469 responses were obtained, with 240 responses from the 2021 batch and 229 responses from the 2022 batch.

Data Collection

A predesigned, semi-structured questionnaire was completed by all participants during their practical class with the help of goggle form. The questionnaire was validated by the statistician of the department.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical analysis was done to analyse the data.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was implied through participation in the study, and confidentiality of responses were maintained.

RESULTS

Table1- Age and Gender wise distribution of students-

MBBS Batch	Mean Age	Males	Females	Total
2021	21.5	102 (42.5%)	138 (57.5%)	240
2022	21.2	134 (58.5%)	95 (41.4%)	229

Table 2: - Awareness & knowledge for FAP-

a) Heard about FAP Before Joining college		
	MBBS 2021	MBBS 2022
Yes	97 (40.4%)	112 (48.9%)
No	143 (59.5%)	117 (51.09%)
b) Source of Information		
Newspaper	18 (7.5%)	12 (5.2%)
Social media	43 (17.9%)	30 (13.1%)
Friend	64 (26.6%)	93 (40.6%)
Others	115 (47.9%)	94 (41.04%)
c) Is FAP Necessary		
Yes	228 (95%)	214 (93.4%)
No	12 (5%)	15 (6.5%)

Table 3: - Experience with FAP on field-

a) Explained visit purpose to family		
	MBBS 2021	MBBS 2022
Yes	238 (99.1%)	223 (97.3%)
No	2 (0.8)	6 (2.6%)
b) Consent Taken		
Yes	237 (98.7%)	221(96.5%)
No	3 (1.25%)	8 (3.4%)
c) Family Cooperation		
Yes	233 (97.08%)	225 (98.2%)
No	7 (2.9%)	4 (1.7%)
d)Families benefited from FAP		
Yes	232 (96.6%)	219 (95.6%)
No	8 (3.3%)	10 (4.3%)

Table 4: - Community Exposure -

Exposure of MBBS Student necessary in First year		
	MBBS 2021	MBBS 2022
Yes	224 (93.3%)	199 (86.8%)
No	16 (6.6%)	30 (13.1%)

Table 5: - Personal growth and support-

a) Communication Skills Improved after interaction		
	MBBS 2021	MBBS 2022
Yes	233 (97%)	215 (93.8%)
No	7 (2.9%)	14 (6.1%)
b) Faculty Support in Field		
Yes	232 (96.2%)	221(96.5%)
No	8 (3.3%)	8 (3.4%)
c) FAP Helps MBBS student in becoming complete IMG's		
Yes	232 (96.6%)	217 (94.7%)
No	8 (3.3%)	12 (5.2%)

The study comprised 469 participants, with 240 from the 2021 batch and 229 from the 2022 batch. The mean age of the participants was 21.5 years for the 2021 batch and 21.2 years for the 2022 batch. The majority of participants were females (57.5% in 2021 and 41.4% in 2022).

A significant proportion of participants (59.5% in 2021 and 51.09% in 2022) reported having not heard about FAP before joining college. Friends were the primary source of information for most participants (26.6% in 2021 and 40.6% in 2022). The majority of participants (95% in 2021 and 93.4% in 2022) believed that FAP is necessary.

Most participants (99.1% in 2021 and 97.3% in 2022) reported explaining the purpose of their visit to the adopted family.

A significant proportion (98.7% in 2021 and 96.5% in 2022) reported taking consent from the adopted family. The majority of participants (97.08% in 2021 and 98.2% in 2022) reported receiving cooperation from the adopted family.

The majority of participants (93.3% in 2021 and 86.8% in 2022) believed that community exposure is necessary for them from their first year itself.

Most participants (97% in 2021 and 93.8% in 2022) reported an improvement in their communication skills after interacting with the adopted family. The majority of participants also (96.2% in 2021 and 96.5% in 2022) reported receiving sufficient faculty support in the field. A significant proportion (96.6% in 2021 and 94.7% in 2022) believed that FAP helps MBBS students become complete Indian Medical Graduates (IMGs).

DISCUSSION

The demographic characteristics of the participants in this study are consistent with those reported in other studies. In a study done by **Patra et al** showed 172 1st year MBBS students with age range of 18-26 years & mean age of 20.58± 1.315 years.³

The results of this study also show that the majority of participants believed that community exposure is necessary for MBBS students in their first year, 66.9% of students responded that FAP was a very good experience. 55.2% of study participants were satisfied with their adopted family. Most of the students were interested to be a part of such activity throughout the professional years.

In another study done by **Amogha Shree et al** Notably, 96.3 % effectively communicated the purposes of visit to the families, and 98.9 % obtained consent before collecting the data. According to the students, cooperative attitudes were observed in 91.5 % of the families; 22 % believed that cooperation might improve with subsequent visits.⁴

FAP plays an important role to become a successful IMG, as indicated in an article written by **Maanvi Padival**, published in Indian Journal of Medical Sciences in 2024⁵

In a study done by **Gaurav RB et al** also stated 98% of the students were told by the families that Family Adoption Program is a good initiative and 02% of the students got response as Family Adoption Program is a scam. Also 98% of the students were told by the allotted families that they will cooperate for this Family Adoption Program in future, 02% of the students were told by the families that they will not cooperate for the same in near future. 04% of the students experienced that their allotted families complained about the hospital attached to the Medical College and remaining 96% of the students didn't receive any complain about the hospital.⁶

Strengths of the Study

This study is notable for its originality, as there is a limited body of existing research exploring this specific area. It provides valuable insights by students in the field, documenting their experiences in detail. Furthermore, the study offers practical recommendations for addressing these challenges, contributing to the improvement and refinement of the Family Adoption Program (FAP) and supporting its successful implementation in medical curricula.

Limitations of the Study

The study acknowledges the limited availability of comprehensive literature on the early stages of the Family Adoption Program (FAP) implementation. Additionally, drawing definitive conclusions about students' perceptions after their first-year exposure to FAP may be premature, as these perceptions are likely to evolve over time. Various factors, including subsequent program experiences, exposure to different patient populations, and academic growth, could influence students' views, making their perceptions dynamic and subject to change as they progress through their medical education.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to discuss the awareness, knowledge, and experience of MBBS students with the Family Adoption Program (FAP). The results show that a significant proportion of participants had heard about FAP before joining college, and most participants believed that FAP is necessary. The study also found that most participants had a positive experience with FAP in the field, with a high level of cooperation from the adopted families. Additionally, the study found that FAP had a positive impact on the personal growth and professional development of MBBS students.

Recommendations-

1. Increase awareness and knowledge of FAP
2. Improve community exposure in MBBS 1st year itself
3. Enhance faculty support through adequate guidance and supervision during FAP
4. Prioritize the effectiveness of FAP amongst undergraduates
5. Making FAP a mandatory part of the medical curriculum in future also.

Conflict of Interest – Nil.

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